

Information Literacy Skills: A Survey of Students in Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the entry-level information literacy skills of first-year students. It is a step towards understanding first-year students' prior information literacy knowledge at Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State. It has broader implications for how librarians understand readiness for library research and the future development of information literacy programmes at the secondary school level. Lack of understanding of prior knowledge by university libraries is a barrier to engaging students in the research process in their first year, as it may result in programs that do not inspire students. The study adopted a survey design, and simple randomization was used to select five faculties from the university. 200 new students were randomly selected from the five faculties to make 1000 students. The Questionnaire was designed and administered during students' library registration. Results showed that students are not taught information literacy skills in secondary schools, and they have little knowledge of information literacy skills. Students' understanding of search strategies, especially in the use of the Boolean operators, was seen to be very poor.

Keywords: Information, Literacy skills, Students, University, Librarians, Delta State

Introduction

Information is available through libraries, community resources, special interest organizations, media, and the Internet—it increasingly comes to individuals in unfiltered formats, raising questions about its authenticity, validity, and reliability. In addition, information is available through multiple media, including graphical, aural, and textual, which pose new challenges for individuals in evaluating and understanding it. The uncertain quality and expanding quantity of information pose large challenges for society. The abundance of information will not create a more informed citizenry without a complementary cluster of abilities necessary to use information effectively. In such a scenario where we expect people to make informed decisions independently, the relevance of information literacy (IL) increases manifold. Be it any organization, association, profession, or irrespective of gender, country, status, age, or other social indicators, IL is and will remain an important dimension. Information literacy (IL) is the term used to describe the efficient and competent handling of information. American Library Association (ALA) describes IL as the ability to locate, evaluate and use information. It is a set of abilities requiring individuals to “recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information.

Information literacy is a concept that has evolved because of recent efforts to move technology-based instruction and research to a level above the long-held concepts previously associated with “computer literacy”. The focus of information literacy education is the development of students' abilities to construct/collect, and analyze information in a way that provides the basis for effective decision-making (Hignite, Margavio & Margavio, 2009). Studies by Parang Raine and Stevenson (2000) revealed that information literacy skills are a fusion of library, computer,

media, technological, critical thinking, ethics, and communication, which, when acquired, would empower individuals to become independent life-long learners. Information literacy has been defined by ACRL (2000), as a set of abilities requiring individuals to “recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information.” It has also been defined as a self-empowering attitude and commitment by individuals and people, at all levels of society, to seek, access, analyse, translate, transform information and create knowledge to solve problems to achieve personal, social, occupational and learning goals for the improvement of their quality of life (IELAJALP 2007).

Research by Bransford (2000) stresses that students come to university with “a range of prior knowledge, skills, beliefs and concepts that significantly influence what they notice about the environment and how they organize and interpret it”. Whatever depth of knowledge the student must have gathered so far, it is expected that the secondary school attended must have had a significant influence on such a student. Basic knowledge in every subject area, especially the most encompassing information literacy, is expected to be learnt from elementary to secondary school, after which it will be consolidated at the university level.

Academic librarians must recognize that building research skills does not always begin in the first year. Existing skills, as reported by Salisbury & Karasmanis (2011), represent a milestone along the lifelong information literacy learning continuum and provide a starting point for building and refining existing skills to suit the university environment. Understanding prior knowledge of incoming students gives librarians knowledge on how to manage the literacy level of the potential of first-year students. It opens up possibilities to improve learning activities to be more relevant to students’ existing skill sets and more likely to support students in their trajectories from peripheral to more engaged participation in learning about university research.

Research Questions

- RQ 1. What is the level of students understanding of information literacy skills from their secondary schools?
- RQ2. What are the most important sources students consult when searching for materials?
- RQ3. What is the capacity of new students to develop information literacy skills?
- RQ4. How familiar are students with the library computer/card catalogue when searching for materials?

Review of Related Literature

Shapiro and Hughes (1996) defined information literacy as “A new liberal art that extends from knowing how to use computers and access information to critical reflection on the nature of information itself, its technical infrastructure and its social, cultural and philosophical context and impact” Information literacy is becoming a more critical part of secondary school education. It is also vital to university-level education (Association of College Research Libraries, 2007). Information literacy is also increasingly important in the contemporary environment of rapid technological change and the proliferation of information resources. Because of the escalating complexity of this environment, individuals are faced with diverse, abundant information choices--in their academic studies, workplace, and personal lives.

Zurkowski (1974) was the first to use the phrase information literacy, which appeared in print written on behalf of the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science. Zurkowski used the phrase to describe the techniques and skills” known by the information literate ‘for utilizing the wide range of information tools and primary sources in moulding information solutions to their problems. Subsequently, some efforts were made to better define

the concept and its relationship to other skills and forms of literacy. Although other educational goals, including traditional literacy, computer literacy, library skills, and critical thinking skills, were related to information literacy and essential foundations for its development, information literacy itself was emerging as a distinct skill set and a necessary key to one social and economic well-being in an increasingly complex information society (Kuhlthau. I 999).

According to ACRL (2000), Information literacy forms the basis for lifelong learning. It is expected in all disciplines, all learning environments, and at all levels of education. It enables learners to master content, extend their investigations, become more self-directed, and assume greater control over their learning. An information-literate individual can:

- Determine the extent of information needed
- Access the needed information effectively and efficiently
- Evaluate information and its sources critically
- Incorporate selected information into one's knowledge base
- Use information effectively to accomplish a specific purpose
- Understand the economic, legal and social issues surrounding the use of information, as well as access and use information ethically and legally.

The rapidly evolving information landscape means that education methods and practices must evolve and adapt accordingly. Computer information literacy must become a key focus of educational institutions at all levels. According to Eisenberg, Lowe and Spitzer (2004), this requires a commitment to lifelong learning and an ability to seek out and identify innovations needed to keep pace with or outpace changes. Within our increasingly information-centric society, educational methods and practices must facilitate and enhance a student's ability to harness the power of information. Key to harnessing the power of information is the ability to evaluate information and ascertain, among other things, its relevance, authenticity and modernity. Fitzgerald (1999) reports that the information evaluation process is a crucial life skill and a basis for lifelong learning. The evaluation consists of several components: metacognition, goals, personal disposition, cognitive development, deliberation, and decision-making. This is both a difficult and complex challenge and underscores the importance of being able to think critically.

Information Literacy and the School Curriculum

Information literacy should occupy an essential role in the school curriculum. Although most schools in developed countries have considered these skills in their curriculum, those who have yet to attain a minimal level of information in society are still lagging behind. The teaching of Information literacy is so important that the American president (Barack Obama) declared October 2009 as information literacy month. He stresses that educators and institutions of learning must be aware of - and adjust to - these new realities in addition to the basic skills of reading, writing, and arithmetic, it is equally vital that our students are given the tools required to take advantage of the information available to them. Obania (2009) added that the ability to seek, find, and decipher information can be applied to countless life decisions, whether financial, medical, educational or technical. Secondary schools are expected to have information literacy embedded in their curriculum, relevant to the country's development level. Because becoming information literate is an active process, requiring seeking out knowledge from multiple sources rather than passively receiving and repeating facts, the teacher's role must evolve from the giver of knowledge into being more of the coach or guide (Wisconsin Educational Media Association, 1993). Studies by Humes (2003) advised that to produce learners who are information literate, schools will need to integrate information literacy skills across the curriculum in all subject areas beginning in the earliest grades. Educational reform and restructuring should make information literacy skills necessary as students seek to

construct their knowledge and create their understandings. Today, instruction methods have changed drastically from the mostly one-directional teacher-student model to a more collaborative approach where the students themselves feel empowered. The American Association of School Librarians published new standards for student learning in 2007, which now inform much of this challenge.

Effective curriculum development is vital to imparting Information Literacy skills to students within the secondary school's environment. Given the already heavy load on students, efforts must be made to avoid curriculum overload Association of College and Research Libraries (2000). Eisenberg strongly recommends adopting a collaborative approach to curriculum development among classroom teachers, librarians, technology teachers, and other educators. Staff must be encouraged to work together to analyze student curriculum needs, develop a broad instruction plan, set information literacy goals, and design specific unit and lesson plans that integrate the information skills and classroom content. These educators can also collaborate on teaching and assessment duties. Many secondary schools have recognized that one way to empower students is to develop a curriculum framework supporting student-centred learning. Rockman (2004) clearly explains what an Information literacy curriculum should entail. It should be problem-based, inquiry-based, and resource-based (using various information resources), effectively use instructional pedagogies and technologies, and be integrated and articulated with a discipline's learning outcomes. Hepworth (2000), Grafstein (2002) and Lupton (2004), who posit that information literacy is best enhanced when it is integrated into the curriculum of another discipline, share this view.

The ACRL (2000) states that gaining skills in information literacy multiplies the opportunities for students' self-directed learning as they become engaged in using a wide variety of information sources to expand their knowledge, ask informed questions and sharpen their critical thinking for still further self-directed learning. Achieving competency in information literacy requires an understanding that this cluster of abilities is not extraneous to the curriculum but is woven into the curriculum's content, structure, and sequence. This curricular integration also allows for furthering the influence and impact of student-centred teaching methods such as problem-based, evidence-based, and inquiry learning. Guided by faculty and others in problem-based approaches, students reason about course content at a deeper level than is possible through the exclusive use of lectures and textbooks. To take the most advantage of problem-based learning, students must often use thinking skills requiring them to become skilled users of information sources in many locations and formats, thereby increasing their responsibility for their learning.

Generally, arguments may be made for Information literacy courses that are either stand-alone or integrated with other courses. Stand-alone courses can meet the needs of the student who recognizes the importance of being information-literate. Parker (2005) reports that it is also practical-oriented and less costly. However, according to Dadzie (2009), stand-alone courses may not motivate students, as they are irrelevant to their assignments or research skills. On the other hand, many authors believe that the ideal method for enabling students to develop the right information literacy skills is by embedding the information literacy activity into the students' course materials. This method allows information literacy to be delivered in the context of the subject students are studying and consolidates the partnership between school librarians and teachers in providing Information literacy training.

Librarians' and Students; Information Literacy Skills

Academic librarians can identify skill gaps based on their experience of working closely with first-year students. Areas readily identified include understanding scholarly information types and finding journal articles (Bemath & Jenkin, 2006; Hartmann, 2001), developing sophisticated search strategies, and evaluating and critically thinking about retrieved information (Crawford & Irving, 2007). However, Guise et al. (2007) reviewed entry-level students' research skills and concluded that they were unprepared to meet the needs of first-year research requirements. Likewise, Russell (2009) identifies significant gaps in "information competencies that students demonstrate during high school to university transition". For example, they lack an understanding of what constitutes quality scholarly information, they have difficulty evaluating information retrieved, and then faced with an array of interfaces and search methods, they favour more intuitive and familiar methods like Google. Rowland (2009) also identified Google as an ingrained "coping behaviour" for university students. It is preferred because it is familiar and simplistic and makes up for a poor understanding of developing sophisticated searching strategies.

Information Literacy Models

Models represent the information-seeking process you go through when seeking information to answer questions, complete an assignment, or explore something you are curious about. The process can be straightforward or very complex—a lot depends on the questions you are trying to answer or the problem you need to solve. Models were developed to define information literacy and outline the information-seeking process (information problem-solving process, the research process). They are like a roadmap for navigating through the information-seeking process. Sometimes, we take one path, and sometimes another—how we find, analyze, and use information depends on many things, including how we learn, the resources available, the tasks in our hands, and what we already know about the topic.

Several widely known models of IL have been developed through research and evaluation. There are many similarities among the models. There is more agreement than disagreement among the models. Some well-known Information Literacy models are Kuhlthau- Information Seeking; Eisenberg & Berkowitz – The Big6 Skills; Irving- Information Skills; Pitts & Stripling – Research Process; New South Wales – Information Process; Loertscher – Information Literacy Model; Follett – Information Skills Model; Netsavy Model; Info Ohio – Dialogue Model; and Society of College, National, and University Libraries (SCONUL) – **Seven Pillars Model**.

SCONUL 7 Pillars of Information Literacy, Core Model for Higher Education: This model has been used to build the Learning outcomes for Information and Research Skills. SCONUL updated its original 7-pillar framework in April 2011 to account for the changing terminology and concepts surrounding information literacy. This new framework is student—and outcome-focused.

1. **Identify:** Able to identify a personal need for information
2. **Scope:** Can assess current knowledge and identify gaps
3. **Plan:** Can construct strategies for locating information and data
4. **Gather:** Can locate and access the information and data they need
5. **Evaluate:** Can review the research process and compare and evaluate information and data
6. **Manage:** Can organize information professionally and ethically

7. **Present:** Can apply the knowledge gained: presenting the results of their research, synthesizing new and old information and data to create new knowledge and disseminating it in various ways.

Methodology

The Dennis Osadebay University Library organizes a library orientation programme for first-year students and lectures a course titled “Use of Library”, which is synonymous with the information literacy program. Students in all faculties enrol in this course, a prerequisite for final graduation. The survey was conducted in the first week of the first semester of 2024 across five major faculties: Agriculture, Management Sciences, Behavioral Sciences, Computing and Environmental Sciences. Data were collected during student registration with the library to maximise the response rate. With a random sampling method, 200 students were selected from the five faculties, making up 1000 students. While the questionnaire was used for data collection, it was administered randomly to the student after their registration exercise for about two weeks. This enables a 100% response rate from students. Data were analyzed using inferential statistics.

Results and Discussion

Biographical data of respondents

Table 1: Gender Distribution of Students

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	518	51.8
Female	482	48.2
Total	1000	100

From Table 1, 51.8% of the students are male, which is less significant than the female counterpart (48.2%).

Table 2: Distribution of Students According to Facilities

Faculties	Frequency	Percentage
Agriculture	200	20.0
Management Science	200	20.0
Behavioural sciences	200	20.0
Environmental Sciences	200	20.0
Computing	200	20.0
Total	1000	100

Table 3: Learning Information Literacy from Secondary Schools Attended

Questions	Yes (2)	No (1)	Mean	Std. Deviation
Teachers encourage the use of libraries and the Internet for information retrieval	748 (74.8%)	251 (25.2%)	1.75	.44
School teaches how to get information from libraries and the internet	466 (46.6%)	534 (53.4%)	1.46	.50
Weighted Average =	1.16			

Table 3 shows that the majority (74.8%) of the students claimed that their teachers encourage using the Library and the Internet for information retrieval, while 53.4% indicated that their school does not teach how to get information from libraries and the Internet. Above all, the weighted average of 1.61 out of 2.00 shows that learning information literacy skills in their respective secondary schools is reasonably good.

Table 4: To become familiar with a subject I know very little, I first consult: Please number in order of importance: 1 = most important ... 8 = least important.

Materials	Most important	Percentage
A journal	28	2.8
Ask a friend	225	22.5
An encyclopedia	38	3.8
A blog	14	1.4
A database	27	2.7
Google	456	45.6
A book	169	16.9
Wikipedia	43	4.3
Total	1000	100

Table 4 shows that the most important materials respondents consult to familiarize themselves with a subject are Google (456 or 45.6%) and Ask a Friend (22.5%).

Table 5: Perceived Capacity of Information Literacy Skills (SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagree).

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	S.D
I could access any library materials with some level of support	4(4)	418 (41.8)	367 (36.7)	211 (21.1)	2.22	.77
I know how to/use the Internet for educational purposes	1(1)	651 (65.1)	279 (27.9)	69 (6.9)	2.58	.62
We were taught how to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information	12 (1.2)	113 (11.3)	212 (21.2)	663 (66.3)	1.47	.96
I had access to internet computer facilities in my secondary school	6(6)	336 (33.6)	437 (43.7)	221 (22.1)	2.15	.96
I can use any of the search engines (Google, Lycos, mamma and Alta Vista) to get any information I want	3 (3)	308 (30.8)	372 (37.2)	317 (31.7)	2.00	.80
I have the ability to seek, find, and decipher information	3(3)	177 (17.7)	319 (31.9)	501 (50.1)	1.68	.77
Frequently access the internet to meet my information needs	2(2)	432 (43.2)	417 (41.7)	149 (14.9)	2.29	.71
What I learnt in my secondary school is enough to help me utilize the library	1 (1)	640 (64.0)	290 (29.0)	69 (6.9)	2.57	.62
I know how to retrieve books/journals from my university library	1 (1)	304 (30.4)	406 (40.6)	289 (28.9)	2.02	.77
We have an information literacy programme embedded in our secondary school curriculum	4(4)	61 (6.1)	72 (7.2)	863 (86.3)	1.21	.56

Weight average	=	2.00
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Table 5 shows that students could not access any library materials without some level of support (Mean = 2.22; SD = 7 taught how to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information (Mean = 1.47; SD = 74) had no access to internet computer facilities in my secondary school (Mean = 2.15; SD= S6). While the majority of the students claimed that they know how to/use the Internet for educational purposes (Mean 2.58; SD = 62). However, overall responses, with a weighted average of 2.00 out of 4.00, show that new students have two capacities for information literacy skills.

Table 6: You used the words ‘business letters’ in a library catalogue search. The computer/card catalogue did not find any items. What do you conclude?

Statement	Response	Percentage
The library does not have any items on this topic	390	39.0
I have not used the right words	210	21.0
All items on this topic are already on loan	232	23.2
The system is down	148	14.8
Do not know	10	3.0
Total	1000	100

Table 6 revealed that 39% of the respondents concluded that the Library has no Items on this topic, while a few others believed that the OPAC system was down. Therefore, it can be concluded that most respondents do not know how to search the library computer/card catalogue with subject terms, as they may not have used the right words.

Findings

The following findings were revealed from the analysis:

- that the students have fairly learnt information literacy skills in their respective secondary schools before getting University admission
- that the most important material a respondent consults in order to be familiar with a subject is Google
- that new students have a low capacity for information literacy skills
- most of the students do not know how to search the library computer/card catalogue with subject terms with little modification

Conclusion

The results of this study provide evidence to accept that students do not bring skills to university that are commensurate with their current educational attainment. The findings demonstrate that entry-level students have few skills that are insufficient for independent research work or library usage. The strong preference for Google is not surprising. It reflects other studies that demonstrate that most students use search engines to begin an information search and are very satisfied with their overall experience of this search method (OCLC, 2006). Students' understanding of search strategies, especially in the use of Boolean operators, was seen to be very poor. Lack of understanding of prior knowledge by university libraries is a barrier to engaging students in the research process in their first year, as it may result in programs that do not inspire students or do not give relevant feedback or encouragement to build on what students already know. The course; “Use of Library” (General Studies) provides a detailed understanding of information literacy skills. Helping students to build on their existing information literacy skills when they start university. With this, they can begin to “develop the intellectual tools and learning strategies to acquire the knowledge that allows people to think

productively. It is recommended that secondary schools include information literacy programmes in their school curriculum while assigning the students the responsibility of putting the school libraries into use.

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